

DISTANT READING STRATEGIES AIDING THE COMPOSITION OF NEW IDIOMATIC MUSIC FOR CLASSICAL GUITAR

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ABSTRACT

Idiomatic music for classical guitar - i.e. music that can accommodate and highlight the specific characteristics and features of the instrument - is an easy task for composers-guitarists but could be a real issue for composers with no specific expertise in guitar music, even more so if they aim to compose adhering to a specific difficulty level. In this context, the aim of this paper is to answer the following questions: can distant reading methods help in defining strategies for composing new idiomatic music for guitar? If so, how can they be defined and implemented? To answer the questions a software has been developed to analyze through distant reading strategies different corpora of music for classical guitar in order to extrapolate knowledge about their idiomatic features in terms of left hand behaviors. The results have been consequently examined and structured with the purpose of mapping idiomatic patterns and to set rules for defining new ones accordingly. Their use have then been tested in the composition of new music for guitar, checking how they fostered creativity, granting at the same time novelty and playability.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Idiomatic music reflects what an instrument can and cannot do, what it does willingly and what it does reluctantly” [1]. In fact, “musical passages can be characterized as more or less idiomatic depending on the extent to which the music relies on instrument-specific effects”. Moreover, “the mechanics of musical instruments commonly influence how the music itself is organized” [2]. However, idiomatic music for guitar seems to be implicitly referred to the traditional repertoire of the instrument, making the two words almost synonymous [3–5]. This raised the questions: are there any ways of aiding and fostering the composition of new music for classical guitar that a performer could feel at the same time idiomatic and new? Can they be defined so that they also assist composers with no expertise in the technique of classical guitar and therefore enriching the repertoire of the instrument? Accordingly,

the goal is to keep the focus at the uncharted possibilities at the core of the idiomatic performance habits of the instrument, leaving out of this research the novelty of the non-conventional extended techniques that are typical, for example, of the avant-garde.

Distant reading is an approach for the studying and understanding of a corpus not by taking into account its texts separately and by having humans reading them, but by aggregating and analyzing them as massive amounts of data with a quantitative approach, usually computerized [6, 7]. It has shown in the last decade its efficacy, mainly for literature and text-based corpora. Moreover, the use of statistics in musicology has recently intensified, especially in studying musical style [8–13], as well as its use for intercepting knowledge of relevance to composers [14, 15].

In this context, the aim of this paper is to answer the following question: can distant reading methods help in defining strategies for composing new idiomatic music for classical guitar? If so, how they can be defined and implemented? To answer it, 1) an algorithm has been developed so to use distant reading methods to intercept in different corpora of scores written for classical guitar some knowledge related to their idiomaticity and difficulty level, 2) the achieved knowledge has been then organized in a way that is accessible and usable by composers for the composition of new music, and finally 3) the effectiveness of the aforementioned algorithm and strategy has been tested qualitatively by one of the two authors, a composer, using it for the composition of a new score, and by the other one, a classical guitarist, who studied and performed it.

2. WHICH IDIOMATICITY?

To define and quantitatively measure idiomaticity, in absolute, is problematic because it is not a binary nor an objective concept. Its perception varies from one person to another, given their unique history and experiences with their instrument and with repertoires and the unique shape of their hands. Furthermore, several elements are involved in the performance of a musical score and in the determination of its idiomaticity and difficulty level, engaging different skills.

For these reasons, this research 1) narrowed down the elements to those that could determine left hand behaviours, i.e. admitted fingerings and transitions between them, and 2) defined an algorithm that takes into account a corpus of scores that is considered idiomatic by a specific (set of)

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guitarist(s), so to satisfy any individual requirement of idiomatcity/difficulty basing it to the repertoire given as an input. The idea is therefore to intercept in the corpus of all the music that is known by and *at the hands* of a performer the admitted and known sequences of left hand fingerings¹ and, from these, to derive new ones to be perceived indeed new and as idiomatic as the original ones.

3. THE SOFTWARE

To implement the algorithm a software has been developed in Python using Music21² and NetworkX³ libraries. It receives as inputs the corpora of scores as collections of files in MIDI and Music XML formats, it parses the complexity of the multiple parts of the scores to a succession of chords through a *salami slicing* method⁴, and retrieves the transitions between each left-hand fingering, enumerating every couple of consecutive chords, as it is depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Bar five from Bach’s *Fugue* BWV 1000 (first line), the same bar after it has been chordified (second line), and the dictionary of the eight possible transitions between chords, thus different left hand fingerings (third line).

The basic idea is that whatever could be the actual fingerings chosen or needed to put into practice the given chords and their succession in time, they must have been learnt by the guitarist(s) to whom the music will be written and they will be perceived the more idiomatic the more often they

¹ For quantitative approaches to the issue of stringed instrument left-hand fingerings see [16–19].

² “Music21 is an object-oriented toolkit for analyzing, searching, and transforming music in symbolic (score-based) forms” started at MIT [20]. <https://web.mit.edu/music21/>

³ NetworkX is a Python package for the creation, manipulation, and study of the structure, dynamics, and functions of complex networks. <https://networkx.github.io>

⁴ A method to “represent musical sequences as ordered collections of consecutive pitch slices, each slice having a proper duration. Every time a new pitch starts or stops being played, the current slice ends and a new one begins. The process applies systematically for every note encountered within the score, including embellishments. This segmentation method, widely used in computational musicology, also goes under the name of pitch simultaneities” or chordification [21].

appear. Thus, by limiting the grammar of a new composition just to the resulting list of couples of chords (evidently put in any order and eventually considering also rests) the idiomatcity of the new score will be granted.

Such an approach has at least the following benefits: 1) working on very common file formats it is fully automatic, quick and reliable, 2) it can work on huge corpora, mixing authors, styles and genres and then possibly triggering new music ideas, 3) it works on the music itself and it does not need data about the fingerings, and 4) it offers a dictionary of chords and a grammar for using them without the need of specific knowledge about the guitar technique for the composers.

A criticality of the software and the constrained composition system hereby described is that it does not consider that the same chord may have two different fingerings in different couples/transitions. This may then result in difficult - if not impossible - sequences in the new music written abiding by the grammar. To fix it the authors are developing a further algorithm to guess the actual fingerings involved and so to list the admitted transitions between chords not only in terms of the music but also of the fingerings.

Furthermore, each of the two file formats accepted as input has its specific advantages and disadvantages. Since music notation refers to conventions that not always show the actual music content (arpeggios, for instance, keep the same fingering but are usually notated in ways that would be salami-sliced in several chords), occasionally a Music XML format could be not the best choice and MIDI is better. Moreover, the enharmonic pitch representation of MIDI files is irrelevant from the point of view of guitar fingering. However, sometimes MIDI files are written so to mimic a performance, tweaking note durations, then resulting in not reliable data after a chordification. In any case, the wide diffusion of music in both formats lets the user decide case by case the one that fits better.

4. A CASE STUDY

To test the effectiveness of the aforesaid software and constrained composition strategy a single score has been given as the input corpus, Leo Brouwer’s *Fugue N. 1* [22]. Despite the shortness of the score, forty-nine bars for less than two minutes and a half of music, the different chord (hence fingering) transitions are totally 334. In table 1 are shown all those with occurrence major than one (ascending), excluding trivial transitions between or including one-note chords. In Fig. 2 all the chords transitions are on the other hand depicted as directed edges on a circular graph where the vertices are the chords. The list given is by itself sufficient for a short constrained new composition.

To ensure a further degree of novelty other chord transitions have been added to the lists: the ones obtained from the 334 translating them horizontally and vertically along the fretboard. This allows an harmonic variety that is also enhanced by the irregularity of the tuning of the strings. In fact, classical guitars are typically tuned in a series of ascending perfect fourths but with a single major third be-

tween the third and the second string⁵. Therefore, any *vertical* translation crossing the tuning kink results in a new sonority.

With the resulting list - and also admitting open string chords and rests in between disconnected transitions - a new score, *Prigioniero I, Op. 49 N. 1b*, of which the first page is shown in Fig. 3, has been composed by one of the authors.

First Chord	Second Chord	Occurrence
D4E4	A3B4	2
G4F5	G4G5	2
G4G5	D4B4G5	2
D4B4G5	F4G4	2
D4C5A5	G4A4	2
F#3G4A4	G3G4A4	2
A3D5G5	A3B4E5	2
D4D5G5	D4B4E5	2
B3B4E5	C4D5G5	2
C4D5G5	C4B4E5	2
B3G4	A3A4	2
D4A4	E4G4	2
E4G4	E4C5	2
E4C5	D4D5	2
D4D5	G4D5	2
G4D5	A4B4	2
G4F#5	C5F#5	2
C5F#5	D5E5	2
D5E5	D5A5	2
D5A5	A3D5B5	2
C4D4	A3D4	2
F3D4	F3G4	2
F4D5Bb5	F4C5Bb5	2
E3E4	E3F#4	2
E3F#4	E3C5	2
E3C5	E3F5	2
E3F5	E3B5	2
E3G#5	E3A5	2
E3A5	E3B4	2
E3B4	E3D5	2
E3D5	E3E5	2
E3G#5	E3F5	2
E3E4	E3G#4	2
E3G#4	E3D5	2
E3D5	E3G5	2
E3G5	E3C#6	2
E3A#5	E3B5	2
E3B5	E3C#5	2
E3C#5	E3E5	2
E3E5	E3F#5	2
E3A#5	E3G5	2
E3E4	E3B4	2
E3B4	E3F5	2
E3F5	E3Bb5	2
E3Bb5	E3E6	2
E3C#6	E3D6	2
E3D6	E3E5	2
E3E5	E3G5	2
E3G5	E3Ab5	2
E3E5E6	E3G5G6	2
E4B4E5	E4D5G5	3
B3D4	B3G4	3
D4D5Bb5	G4Bb5	3
G4Bb5	F4D5Bb5	3
A3A4	D4A4	4
A3D5B5	C4F5D6	4
E3B5	E3G#5	4
E3E6	E3C#6	4
E4D5G5	E4B4E5	5
E3C#6	E3A#5	6

Table 1. All the chord transitions in Brouwer's *Fugue N. 1* with occurrence major than one (ascending), excluding trivial transitions between, or including, one-note chords.

The new score has then been studied by the second author, a guitarist, who had Brouwer's score in her reper-

⁵ From the lowest string, to the highest: EADGBE.

Figure 2. All the chords transitions in Brouwer's *Fugue N. 1* depicted as directed edges on a circular graph where the vertices are the chords.

toire, and who confirmed the easiness of learning it and the friendliness of the fingering involved. However, as a result of the chords obtained from translations along the fretboard and of newfound sequences, the score has not been experienced by the performer as a sibling of the corpus piece, but as an original new one.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The experience presented connected the artistic practice of the two authors, a composer and a guitarist, trying to provide answers to artistic issues by the means of technology and through research.

Looking for strategies for composing new idiomatic music for guitar that could be useful also for composers with no experience with the instrument, a software has been developed to analyze through distant reading strategies different corpora of music in order to map idiomatic patterns in transitions between left hand fingerings and to set rules for defining new ones accordingly. Their use has then been tested in the composition of new music for guitar, checking how it fostered creativity, granting at the same time novelty and playability.

Future developments will refine the algorithm recognizing the actual fingerings involved and perfecting the software's usability, so to offer a system that could also automatically provide the composer an enlarged and user-

Prigioniero I

Op. 49 N. 1b

Festante

Giovanni Albinì (*1982)

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Figure 3. First page of the score composed by one of the authors with the constrained system based on the list of chord transitions obtained from Brouwer's *Fuga N. 1*.

friendly list including all the translations along the fretboard. Moreover, to address the issue formalizing left-hand fingering/position changes only is not without its flaws: to study them taking also into account other parameters - such as for instance tempos and durations - could help in inferring their idiomaticity more effectively and in more detail. Further studies will be conducted then to test the efficiency of the strategy surveying the experience of several different performers and composers.

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